

Feasibility Study:

Digital Visualization of Burial Mounds in Verdal

Project Report

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Table of Contents:

Introduction	2
Case Study - The Construction of a Burial Mound	2
Optimisation for XR Experience and Future Solutions	8
Relevant Advances in Real-Time Rendering	9
In-Game Data Streaming	12
Conclusion and Recommendations for Future Research	16

Introduction

As a case study, we present a pedagogical experience that covers constructional and ceremonial aspects of burial mounds during the Migration Period, in Verdal Norway. The content is essentially presented as a linear narrative (film), but the sequence *could* be experienced in VR, as all graphic elements are assembled in a game engine. This also means that future adaptations for geo-referenced AR may utilize the same content as a basis.

Expanding on the case study itself, we also present technical tests relating novel approaches to real-time CGI, to demonstrate how VFX quality CG-assets may be implemented in real-time applications through the use of extremely dense photogrammetric models and novel capabilities in real-time rendering. On a similar note, we demonstrate how in-game data-streaming technology can bring GIS-data to game engines. Based on these tests, we then offer some deliberations that may be instrumental for strategizing a potential main project: XR contents surrounding Stiklestad and the national anniversary in 2030.

Case Study - The Construction of a Burial Mound

In our case study, we focused on burial mounds from the migration period (around 500 AD); in the area of Vinne, at Verdal Norway. The goal was to convey how these burial mounds were constructed, and how a typical burial ceremony may have unfolded. While the content was to be historically accurate, we needed to tell the story in a way pedagogically suitable for families and school children. As such, significant attention was devoted to

pre-production, in order to arrive at the final version of the screenplay and storyboard (Fig 1) in close collaboration with consulting experts.

Figure 1

Storyboard

Note: The storyboard makes camera choices for the film, but also solves the sequence of events for XR. It served as a useful collaborative tool.

Next, the task was to bring the sequence to life in a medium that allowed for both video and XR output. We opted to experiment with a beta-version of Unreal Engine 5 (UE5), by Epic Games. The location had previously been scanned using lidar technology by local company Biodrone AS. They were able to provide a mesh of the area consisting of one million polygons. The mesh was treated in Blender by removing modern buildings in the area and then imported into UE5. This provided a very accurate representation of the terrain as of the area.

To increase performance of the scene, a novel technology for real-time mesh optimization, *Nanite*, was used to generate a virtualized mesh. While the terrain mesh was not the most significant performance factor in the final scene, enabling Nanite did increase performance significantly. With the scene running on high fidelity settings Nanite increased performance from 20 fps to 30 fps (Fig 2).

Figure 2

Nanite, for real-time mesh optimization

Note: A visualization of the nanite enabled terrain mesh.

To populate the area with vegetation, third party assets were used. This included assets from Epic Megascans library and foliage from Landscape Pro pack in the Unreal Marketplace. The use of foliage was the most significant factor on performance in the scene. To further increase the performance the DLSS 2.0 technology from Nvidia was used for upscaling. Enabling DLSS gave a significant performance increase of 15-20 Fps in the scene. And in some cases an increase of up to 40 fps with ultra performance settings.

A simple method of gathering this data was using a mobile app for IOS called HDReye (The Young Astronauts, 2021). This enabled an easy method to photograph a High Dynamic Range photo sphere and stitch the photos together as a single HDR Image. The HDR data was gathered on location in Vinne and imported into Unreal. Using Unreal Engine's HDRIBackdrop function, Unreal was able to generate the lighting in the scene based on the HDR Image (Fig 3).

Figure 3

HDRI-lighting

Note: HDRI-lighting is increasingly used for real-time applications

Fire effects and smoke were produced using Unreal particle systems, for which the team experimented with some custom setups controlled by Blueprint scripts (Fig 4).

Figure 4

Dynamic particle effects

Note: Screenshot from the final film.

CG-characters were developed using conventional production methodologies, optimizing for real-time application (Fig 5). The art direction relied on field trips to Stiklestad Museum, where we secured photo references of garments and relevant accessories, as well as plausible color schemes (Fig 6).

Figure 5

CG-Characters

Note: The characters were produced in a neutral A-pose to optimize future utility

Figure 6

Reference gathering Stiklestad

Note: In future productions, we would also like to utilize *actual* artifacts such as jewelry, weaponry etc., as items for photogrammetry—see the later segment on photogrammetric methods for Unreal Engine.

The scope of the case-study would not permit rigging or animation, yet the characters were produced in neutral A-poses to maximize future utility. To tell our story, however, the neutral models needed to be adapted to key poses; produced by a digital sculpt per pose. As the characters consisted of several meshes, this process was facilitated by the *Transpose*

Subtools function in ZBrush (Fig 7). The various character poses were then imported to UE5 and linked up with the relevant materials (Fig 8).

Figure 7

CG-Characters posed

Note: *Transpose Subtools* function in ZBrush allowed the characters to be sculpted into various poses.

Figure 8

Character Ensemble (posed)

With additional assets mainly from Epic Megascans library, the posed characters could interact with the virtual world and act out our story (Fig 9).

Figure 9

Posed Character in the scene

Note: Posed character with other scene elements. Shot from the final film.

In Norum & Voldseth, 2022, from:

https://drive.google.com/file/d/1u3d-tzCyw0GMOxmZ_iidnwakUg2ZBYIz/view?usp=sharing

While the final version of the film adheres to the storyboard as such, it does contain minor inaccuracies and elements that could benefit from refinement. Due to the limitations of the study, however, we could not iterate further at this stage.

Optimisation for XR Experience and Future Solutions

We wanted to explore the possibility of using the workflow for the film as part of an XR experience. Recent developments in real time rendering technology in Unreal Engine have made the workflow for XR experiences smoother and more in line with traditional game or virtual production workflows. There is, however, still a substantial amount of optimisation needed for a good experience in VR. There are also new features in Unreal Engine that we used in our case study that are currently unsupported in XR experiences. Nanite & Lumen being examples of this. As of October 2022, Epic has announced that Nanite & Lumen will be able to support XR experiences in Unreal Engine 5.1 slated for release later this year.

In our case study we also looked at Nvidia's Deep Learning Super Sampling technology (DLSS). Enabling the DLSS feature in the project gave an additional average frame rate of 10-20 FPS depending on scalability settings. Future developments in DLSS could also help close this gap in performance needed for XR experiences. DLSS 3.0 which will be supported in Nvidia's 40 series graphics cards claims to be able to boost frame rates by up to 4x (Lin & Burns, 2022).

To learn about the performance gap for XR in our case study we tried to optimize our scene for a VR experience. The steps taken to gain an optimized viewing experience in XR involved turning off Lumen and Nanite, reducing foliage in the scene, and downsampling the terrain mesh to reduce draw calls in the engine. Meshes used from quixel megascans were also reduced in fidelity.

Several rendering optimisations were enabled in the engine using our case study. Among these are using MSAA anti aliasing instead of TAA, enabling forward shading in the project and instanced stereo. Forward shading provides a faster baseline rendering in Unreal Engine compared to deferred rendering. Providing a performance boost needed for XR experience and also increases visual fidelity as it works better with anti aliasing. The drawback with forward shading is that it supports fewer features in materials for assets.

Instanced stereo is another rendering feature that was enabled for better performance. Instanced stereo gives a performance boost in XR situations and uses a more optimized flow for rendering each eye for stereo. A test using all of these optimizations mentioned was conducted. With the optimisations enabled there was a substantial lift in performance headroom which allowed for use of dynamic lights in the scene like fire FX. (Fig 10)

Figure 10

VR-test

Note: Optimized VR-test.

Voldseth, 2022, from:

https://drive.google.com/file/d/11dF1dZkyQGiL4cuVVn-iApIIRX_CNClc/view?usp=sharing

Relevant Advances in Real-Time Rendering

As demonstrated in our case study, we have experimented with Epic Games' beta-version of Unreal Engine 5. The scope of the case study did not permit a full demonstration of its technological implications. This *full* potential is, nonetheless, important to consider when strategizing for future productions.

While we have briefly accounted for them, we will summarize what we find to be the most impactful novelties; *Lumen GI and Reflections* (Epic, 2021 a) which is an efficient method for real-time Global Illumination (GI). *Nanite Virtualized Geometry* (Epic, 2021 b) which automatically reduces the number of polygons for 3D models without the need for conventional level of detail models (LODs). And *Streaming Virtual Texturing* (Epic, 2021 c)

that enables significantly increased texture resolution. In sum, we can now produce real-time worlds with a practically unlimited number of polygons, textured with ultra-high texture resolutions, dynamically illuminated with real-time GI—all without the conventional limitations of CG-production for real-time application. This potential is perhaps best exemplified in a demo launched in connection with the motion picture *Matrix Awakens* (Fig. 11).

Figure 11

The Matrix Awakens: An Unreal Engine 5 Experience.

Note: Extremely dense real-time virtual world in UE5. Reprinted from Unrealengine.com,

In Epic Games, 2021e, from <https://www.unrealengine.com/en-US/wakeup>

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As an alternative to optimizing content for real-time XR of today, we may instead divert resources to obtain as densely detailed CG-content as possible—assured that such data may seamlessly serve XR-experiences in the near future. This may include photogrammetric models of significant resolution. While we *did* use a moderately dense photogrammetric model of the landscape in question—provided by Biodrone AS—such elevation data would best be derived from lidar-capture. The location itself, in the middle of a field, was a *particularly* unsuitable subject for photogrammetry. As for the CG-characters, these were

produced by conventional methods for real-time optimization. The case study, as such, was not instrumental to demonstrate Nanite and its true impact of real-time optimization of highly dense geometry.

Therefore, to complement the case study, we include an example of simultaneous artistic research using UE5, achieved using highly dense photogrammetrical models (Fig 12)

Figure 12.

Photogrammetric Test in UE5

Note: Dense real-time scene in UE5 with photogrammetric models. Herengracht, Amsterdam.

In Norum, 2021a, from <https://vimeo.com/598776260>

The scene consists of a number of copies of the same building, each of about 10 million polygons. The physical setting is photographed (in this case over 1000 images), on a dry, cloudy day with good lighting conditions. Here, a polarizing filter was also applied to limit reflections. The resulting dense point cloud produced using Reality Capture resulted in an initial mesh of about 250 million polygons. The mesh was gradually optimized and UV-mapped using UDIMs, which allows texturing through several high-resolution

image-maps—a method traditionally limited to pre-rendered VFX. This demonstrates how *Nanite Virtualized Geometry* and *Streaming Virtual Texturing* allow far richer detail compared to previous techniques for real-time CGI. In future tests, exporting the model in parcels will be explored as a method to achieve even higher in-game fidelity.

The potential for extreme levels of detail will mark future VR experiences, as it represents the medium in which participants may truly observe surfaces in close proximity. In our context, we can imagine future digital reproductions of archeological artifacts in ultra-high resolution, or e.g. digital reproductions of clothing, decoration, weaponry etc.

In-Game Data Streaming

Another aspect that fell outside the scope of the case study is the use of geospatial data in-game. This was, however, initially outlined as a promising potential for future research. As such, we surveyed and experimented with the current state of such technology, to assess the degree to which it would be applicable for smaller production teams of CG-artists (such as ourselves). The application of geospatial data could be useful in order to generate surrounding topography—to aid with large scale set-design. Accurate world positioning might also allow adapting the content to location-based experiences for Augmented Reality (AR)—we envision AR-content to enrich the experience for future visitors to the fields of Vinne and the surrounding area of Stiklestad.

The use of Geographical Information Systems (GIS) data as a basis for game-worlds is an established practice. A recent example is the use of height-data from The Norwegian Mapping Authority in the production of *The Battle of Narvik*, for the multiplayer game *Battlefield V* (DICE, 2018). We should note that such elevation-models only serve as a crude basis upon which significant artistry and “set dressing” is required. This is likely to remain the case. However, level design is increasingly facilitated by advances in auto-generation of

foliage and other procedurally-driven elements—the aforementioned example from the Matrix relies heavily on procedural creation using Houdini (McKenzie, 2022).

While games such as Battlefield make use of GIS-data, the gameplay remains confined to a “sandbox” map. The next level for GIS-implementation makes use of large scale streaming; as a segue from *Virtualized Texture Streaming* already mentioned, similar technology is at play here. One notable example, which garnered great interest at its release, is *Microsoft Flight Simulator 2020* (Asobo Studio, 2020). For those who remember installing computer games from DVDs; *Microsoft Flight Simulator 2020* would require at least 1.7 million such disks (Parijat, S. 2020). This enormous amount of data (the entire world) is streamed into the engine using Microsoft Bing servers (similar to Google Maps or Apple Maps), which amounts to about 2PB of data storage. For this project, we tested the same streaming technology using *Cesium Ion* for Unreal Engine 4 (Fig 13).

Figure 13

Geo-Reference Test

Note: Geo-reference test using Cesium Ion and UE4 (Now available for UE5).

In Norum, 2021b, from <https://vimeo.com/650907723>

In the test, geo-data from Microsoft Bing provides the orthophoto as seen, as well as the background height-map. For the mid-range landscape—the vicinity of Nedre By, at Vinne in Verdal—a higher resolution height-map was acquired from The Norwegian Mapping

Authority. This data was also uploaded to the Cesium Ion server, and similarly streams into the engine. In the video, an artistic “set dressing” is also provided. The example demonstrates an approach for a real-time virtual world in various levels of complexity (Fig 14).

Figure 14

Various levels of detail

Note: Foreground: artistic set-dressing, midground: detailed height-data, background: general height-data from mapping service.

In Norum, 2021b, from <https://vimeo.com/650907723>

We can extrapolate a methodology here as it would relate to virtual world building, in three levels of increasing complexity;

- (1) macro: the surrounding large scale world, as it streams directly from a world mapping service; in this example, Microsoft Bing.
- (2) meso: the mid-range environment in higher resolution; in this case derived from the Norwegian Mapping Authority.
- (3) micro: the highly detailed immediate environment with artistic set-dressing.

For a project with larger scope, a more complex virtual world might be developed according to this methodology; in that scenario, lighting could be achieved through real-time dynamic

lighting (as demonstrated)—as opposed to the HDRI method outlined in our case study. This would, for instance, allow dynamic day/night cycles, as well as changing weather conditions (Fig 15).

Figure 15

Dynamic Day & Night cycles

Note: Dynamic day & night cycles and weather patterns for a fully immersive world

In Norum, 2021b, from <https://vimeo.com/650907723>

Regarding location-based AR, we briefly tested a pre-release of the Esri SDK for UE4. This proved to be, as yet, an unattainable solution for a team without dedicated software developers—exceeding the limitations of this study. However, as the world leader in GIS, Esri remains in close collaboration with both Unity and Unreal game engines for native implementation of geospatial coordinates (Esri, 2021a). At the time of writing, the production release of the Esri SDK for both Unity and Unreal is expected in June of 2022 (Esri, 2021b), which will include more user-friendly AR-implementation (Esri, 2022c, 42:30). This technology makes a perfect case for follow-up research.

In other words, geo-referenced content is likely to become accessible to small production teams of CG-artists, very soon. Such native implementation of geospatial

coordinates in-game will afford AR-productions a more streamlined emphasis on artistic content and storytelling.

Conclusion and Recommendations for Future Research

The novel technological developments we have tested; *Lumen GI and Reflections* (Epic, 2021 a), *Nanite Virtualized Geometry* (Epic, 2021 b), *Streaming Virtual Texturing* (Epic, 2021 c), as well as geospatial data streaming by Cesium Ion (Cesium GS, 2022) and Esri (Esri, 2022b.), all lead to an interesting conclusion: We may construct a complex virtual world that in principle could serve both multiplayer VR, geo-referenced AR, interactive gaming experiences, as well as film projects. In future research, with perspectives towards the national anniversary in 2030—with Stiklestad at the center of events—these are inspiring potentials.

As such, we suggest that resources be devoted to the creation of highly dense content, where what used to be considered film quality CG-assets are created for multi-purpose use. This strategy could be seen opposed to production of real-time applications for immediate utility, with soon antiquated limitations such as reduced poly-budgets, light-baking (for which separate UVs must be created), and models of various levels of detail (LODs). The baking of conventional real-time image-maps, i.e. normal- and parallax-maps, etc., also needs reconsideration in further real-time tests, in order to arrive at “best practices” for multi-purpose CGi production. Further testing of such approaches to Physically Based Rendering (PBR) for complex real-time assets should therefore be elements in continued research.

In addition, we urge the continued exploration of streamed GIS-data, serving the twofold goal of, a: optimizing methods for geo-referenced AR, and b: continued exploration of set-design stemming from such data. We contend that Esri is likely to provide the most robust solution, whose developers seem to suggest that for combining highly detailed

(custom) lidar-data with their data-sets, a potential method is to simply implement custom 3d-meshes (Esri, 2021)—similar to the solution for our ground mesh in the case study. This is one of many pragmatic production strategies that remain to be explored, as to best draw benefits from the technologies we have outlined.

An important aspect, somewhat obscured by a technical report, is the fundamental importance of storytelling. While the pre-production made for a time-consuming part of our case-study, the resulting storyboard served as an invaluable tool for all parties involved. The physical meetings and relevant field trips involving the researchers, student interns, and consulting experts stand out as particularly productive. This approach ensured an inspired shared vision. As our consultants pointed out: the conceptual phase itself made for the most memorable and rewarding part of the project.

Finally, after this study, we are aware of the multitude of additional resources and competences which the larger vision of Stiklestad 2030 would need to draw upon. Future projects—or perhaps simultaneously funded projects—should seek synergies with, i.e: actors, historians, musicians, geographers, geologists and archaeologists.

However, when it comes to the novel methodologies of XR-production, *some* future small-scale projects might benefit from a more narrow focus; such as *specifically* geo-referenced AR, photogrammetric acquisition of actual artifacts, digital character mocap, etc., which in all cases may be explored with a very *limited* scope in terms of storytelling. The broad approach of this case study proved challenging, as we attempted to convey an historically accurate narrative through a CG-production, while simultaneously carrying out technical research.

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